

Internal Stresses in Frontally-Polymerized Composites

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Radical Induced Cationic Frontal Polymerization

Composite processing

(Staal et al. 2023)

Do parts manufactured by Frontal Polymerization (FP) meet industry performance requirements?

1m FP rotor blade, KVE

Internal Stresses

t=7s

t=24s

Is the sharp gradient in both temperature and degree of cure creating internal stresses?

(Chen et al. 2023)

1. Chemical shrinkage
2. Thermal expansion, mismatch in CTE
3. Tool part interaction

➔ Introduce dimension instabilities, poor mechanical performances

(Wu et al. 2025)

(Gentz et al. 2004)

Manufacturing setup

(Staal, 2023)

(Saertex)

Resin	ECC monomer
Thermal Initiator	Benzopinacol
Photo-initiator	IOC-8 SbF6
Fabric	Saertex Magic Flow UD, 704g/m ²
Gel	Precured FP-acrylate resin

DIC analysis

- Tows encapsulated in resin-rich areas
- Cutting to release locked-in transverse residual stress
- Open-source Digital Image Correlation tool: Ncorr

Parameters Selection

Frontal Polymerization (FP) samples

- High reactivity
- Low reactivity

Reference sample:

- Bulk curing with anhydride hardener at 150°C

Curing profiles

- Higher reactivity: higher T_{max}
- Higher reactivity is prone to large T overshoot for thermocouples in resin-rich areas

Sample	T_{max} (°C)	Time above T _g (s)	V (mm/s)	Cooling rate (°C/min)
FP High Reactivity	220	284	0.65	3.7
FP Low Reactivity	195	140	0.45	4.1

Micrographs before cutting

- High Reactivity: higher temperature for higher amount of time
- Cracks occur more frequently on top (Gel)

Micrographs after stress-release

High Reactivity

Low Reactivity

- Cracks are located at the bottom: no pre-existing cracks
- For most of the sample: no discernable impact of the stress-release

Reference Oven

Strain-Stress results

- Pre-existing cracks: top part relaxed prior to the cut
- Bottom cracks do not go through the whole thickness

U-displacements

Sample	Magnitude	Direction	Possible Origin
FP High Reactivity	++	→ compression	Thermal Expansion
FP Low Reactivity	-	→ compression	Thermal Expansion
Reference Oven	+	← tension	Chemical Shrinkage

FP High Reactivity

FP Low Reactivity

Reference Oven

U-displacements

The front is pushing the resin away from it:

- High expansion phenomena
- Fast curing system could lock-in the displacements

FP Low Reactivity

Reference Oven

(Chen et al. 2023)

σ_{11} estimation

Small strain assumption: $\epsilon_{11} = \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\delta u}{\delta e_v} + \frac{\delta v}{\delta e_u} \right)$

Plane stress assumption: $\sigma_{11} = \frac{E}{1-\nu^2} \epsilon_{11} + \frac{E\nu}{1-\nu^2} \epsilon_{22}$

< 34MPa; tensile strength of FP resin

(Tarafdar et al. 2023)

Method limitations:

- Resolution is not high enough to capture the fiber-matrix interface
- Sensitive to changes in speckles geometry and dimension

~ 20MPa

FP High Reactivity

~ 4MPa

FP Low Reactivity

~ 10MPa

Reference Oven

Conclusion

- Frontal Polymerization (FP) can introduce damage and higher level of internal stresses
- Optical analysis can be used to estimate residual stresses within FP produced laminates
- The magnitude of internal stresses and damage made by FP can be controlled
- Their impact on actual mechanical and dimensional properties remains to be established

Thank you for your attention!

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Manufacturing setup

- Vacuum assisted resin transfer molding of 150x150mm UD carbon composites
- Frontal polymerization initiated inside the inlet tube

Method Error

- Same sample, uncut, 2 scans of the same region
- Sample is moved to introduce rigid body motion

Strain-Stress results

Curing profiles

- Non-assisted FP: top part remains at higher T°
- Oven-assisted FP: middle part remains at higher T°
- Higher reactivity: higher max T°
- Transverse curing: lower max T°

FP high reactivity 1 Before

FP high reactivity 1 After

FP low reactivity Before

FP low reactivity After

Oven 1 Before

Oven 1 After

FP low reactivity Before

FP low reactivity After

FP Oven curing Before

FP Oven curing After

FP high reactivity 2 Before

FP high reactivity 2 After

FP transverse curing Before

FP transverse curing After

FP Oven curing Before

FP Oven curing After

FP high reactivity 2 Before

FP high reactivity 2 After

Curing profiles

- Higher reactivity: higher T_{max}
- Non-assisted FP: top part remains at higher T_{max}
- Oven-assisted FP: middle part remains at higher T_{max}
- Transverse curing: lower T_{max}

Sample	T_{max} (°C)	Time above Tg (s)	V (mm/s)
FP High Reactivity	220	284	0.65
FP Low Reactivity	195	140	0.45
FP Transverse curing	185	61	1.54
FP Oven curing	250	482	/
Oven	155	18270	/

Internal Stresses

1. Chemical shrinkage due to the volumetric change during polymerization
 2. Thermal expansion, mismatch in CTE
 3. Tool part interaction
- ➔ Introduce dimension instabilities, poor mechanical performances

V-Notched shear testing:

- Polyamide resin
- Stress at significant onset of acoustic emission vs stress at maximum load

(Wu et al. 2025)

(Gentz et al. 2004)